

Step 4. Questionnaire

For each of these categories, we will give an idea of the current distribution in the music industry. Then, we ask you to please indicate how important it is that such music is **recommended more on music streaming services**:

Q1

31.4% of the 5,000 most played songs on the radio in 2023 were in the pop genre, followed by rock at 8.8% and country at 8.7%. For each of the 100 most streamed songs and artists on Spotify in 2023, nearly half belonged to the pop genre.¹

How important is it that music from **genres other than pop** is recommended more on music streaming services?

Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Neither Agree nor Disagree / Agree / Strongly Agree

Q2

In 2023, only 13,8% of songs were streamed >1000 times on Spotify.² Recommender systems, that are prone to 'popularity bias' (disproportionally recommending things that are already popular), may amplify the difference between popular and less-popular music.³ This has financial implications for lesser-streamed artists.

How important is it that music from **lesser-known artists** is recommended more on music streaming services?

Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Neither Agree nor Disagree / Agree / Strongly Agree

Q3

In songs from the Billboard Top 100 from 2012-2022, women comprised 22.3% of all artists, 12.8% of all songwriters, and 2.8% of all producers. Non-binary artists had 3 songs listed in total.⁴

How important is it that music from **underrepresented genders** is recommended more on music streaming services?

Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Neither Agree nor Disagree / Agree / Strongly Agree

Q4

The US and Canada combined receive a 40,9% market share of the global music industry revenue. 7,5% of the world's global population lives on this continent.⁵

How important is it that music from **underrepresented countries** is recommended more on music streaming services?

Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Neither Agree nor Disagree / Agree / Strongly Agree

¹ Chartmetric, <https://reports.chartmetric.com/2023/year-in-music/part-1>

² Luminata, <https://luminatedata.com/reports/yearend-music-industry-report/>

³ Ekstrand, M. D., Tian, M., Azpiazu, I. M., Ekstrand, J. D., Anuyah, O., McNeill, D., & Pera, M. S. (2018). *All The Cool Kids, How Do They Fit In?: Popularity and Demographic Biases in Recommender Evaluation and Effectiveness* Proceedings of the 1st Conference on Fairness, Accountability and Transparency, Proceedings of Machine Learning Research. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/ekstrand18b.html>

⁴ USC Annenberg <https://assets.uscannenberg.org/docs/aii-inclusion-recording-studio-jan2023.pdf>

⁵ IFPI 2024, United Nations 2022

Voting

For each of these categories, we will give an idea of the current distribution in the music industry. Then, we ask you to please indicate how important it is that such music is recommended more on music streaming services:

31.4% of the 5,000 most played songs on the radio in 2023 were in the pop genre, followed by rock at 8.8% and country at 8.7%. For each of the 100 most streamed songs and artists on Spotify in 2023, nearly half belonged to the pop genre.

I feel that music from genres other than pop should be recommended more on music streaming services.
 Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree

In 2023, only 13.8% of songs were streamed >1,000 times on Spotify, recommender systems, that are prone to 'popularity bias' (disproportionally recommending things that are already popular), may amplify the difference between popular and less-popular music. This has financial implications for lesser-streamed artists.

I feel that music from lesser-known artists should be recommended more on music streaming services.
 Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree

In songs from the Billboard Top 100 from 2012-2022, women comprised 22.3% of all artists, 12.8% of all songwriters, and 2.8% of all producers. Non-binary artists had 3 songs listed in total.

I feel that music from artists from an underrepresented gender should be recommended more on music streaming services.
 Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree

The US and Canada combined receive a 40.9% market share of the global music industry revenue. 7.5% of the world's global population lives on this continent.

I feel that music from underrepresented countries should be recommended more on music streaming services.
 Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree

Submit

Results

This table shows your previous selection

Music from genres other than pop	Music from lesser-known artists	Music from artists from an underrepresented gender	Music from underrepresented countries
Neither agree nor disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Neither agree nor disagree

This graph shows data from a previous study

Finish

Then, the moderator ask the final question:

- What are your thoughts on the comparison between your own choices and the data from the previous study?

This ends the study. We stop the recording and thank the participant.